

The Role of the Inafist Dactyloscopy in the Murder Investigation Process (Case study at Polda Central Java)

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ABSTRACT: One of the fingerprints as evidence in the process of handling a crime, especially in handling the crime of murder, the Police are authorized or entitled to take several actions that have been regulated or determined by the Law on the Indonesian National Police No. 2 of 2002 in article 15 paragraph (1), (dactyloscopy) in the investigation process is as technical assistance in carrying out investigations and is very important to assist investigators in uncovering or resolving a criminal act that occurred. the obstacles that occur are both external and internal barriers with various solutions in murder cases because the success or failure of obtaining fingerprints is influenced by the surrounding circumstances.

KEYWORDS: Dactyloscopy, Criminal Actors, Murder

A. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, law is very important to regulate people's lives. Law is a set or number of rules that essentially become a benchmark and guideline for residents of a country so that their behavior does not conflict with general habits in people's lives and does not conflict with matters that offend the public. One legal expert, namely Utrecht (cited by Kansil) argued that according to law are various kinds of rules relating to human life, whether in the form of orders or things that are prohibited as a reference for social life which must be obeyed together. Mobilization greatly influences the development of the world and the nation. . Along with the faster developments that occur in the world, the more crimes that occur. Apart from the large population, it is also due to the low level of the economy and education of the community members (Rudi Alfahri Rangkuti, 2020)

Modern society has the characteristic of carrying out more mobility, making humans increasingly change their activities (Mohamad Dimiyati Ayatullah, 2019). Disclosing a crime is the main task of the police agency, as the sole investigator in Indonesian general criminal cases, therefore investigators are required to work hard in searching for and finding evidence that has something to do with the crime that occurred, in turn the perpetrators can be arrested. So in terms of finding and collecting evidence, the investigator must know where and how he started his activities in order to achieve the desired goal, namely the disclosure of a crime. which can be seen clearly and there are also those that require observation techniques using certain knowledge that is useful for further data management. In relation to a criminal act that occurred, the place that the investigator first visited or processed was the place of confinement

In the 1945 Constitution, it has been explained that the State of Indonesia is a State based on law and not based on power, the State of Indonesia is a country that is democratic and upholds values based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. the rules that guarantee the rights and obligations of a person and society, with the existence of law in Indonesia creates harmony in the life of society, nation and state.

Starting from the idea that in carrying out activities, consciously or not, some of these actions can be seen and some require observation techniques using certain knowledge that is useful for further data management. In relation to a criminal act that occurred, the place visited or processed by the investigator first is the place where the crime was committed, which is called the TKP (Pekaa Judicial Place).

In positive law, evidence can be in the form of witness statements, expert statements, letters, instructions and statements of the accused. In practice, criminal procedural law is confirmed in the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHP) in Article 184, the valid evidence is is; To be able to find such evidence, an investigation phase must be carried out first, namely a process of searching and collecting evidence (KUHP).

The suspect The investigation process will be carried out through several stages, one of which is by taking fingerprints . The investigation process will be carried out through several stages, one of which is by taking fingerprints. Fingerprints, which in English are called fingerprints, are taken during the investigation process to further examine evidence that may have been left at the TKP. The results achieved from the investigation are a knowledge called dactyloscopy or knowledge about fingerprints.

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Scientific Crime Investigation is an investigative process in which the evidentiary system makes use of science and technology or makes use of forensic functions (Forensic Identification, Forensic Laboratory, Forensic Psychology, Forensic Medicine and other forensic experts). The word Dactyloscopy comes from the Greek Dactylos which means finger and Scopium which means to see, researching, studying. It was first developed by Francis Galton, who in 1888 entered into a collaboration with Sir William Herschell to carry out scientific investigations regarding patterns of finger lines and devised a system for dividing and regarding types of people (Muhammad Ibnu Fauzan, 2020)

"It was shown that fingerprints are more than morphologie and put forward the four most important things to be able to assert one's identity: fixed, firm, diverse and easy to register and organize" Dactyloscopy is the science that studies fingerprints for the purpose of re-recognition identify people by observing the lines on the lines of the fingers and soles of the feet. Dactyloscopy comes from the Greek words dactylos which means fingers or finger lines, and scopein which means observing or researching. Then, from that understanding, the term in English arose, dactyloscopy, which we know, became the science of fingerprints.

In the science of fingerprints (Dactyloscopy) states that no human being has the same fingerprints and will not change for the rest of his life. Because of its permanent nature, fingerprints "The use of fingerprints for identification has been growing all over the world, especially in developed countries. The sweat that is found on the palms and fingers will leave traces on objects that are held or touched. In this regard, Dactyloscopy or the science of fingerprints has urged other identification methods because it is very practical and accurate, (Andi Hamzah, 1984)

Crimes that require dactyloscopy as a means of proof, for example the crime of intentional or premeditated murder and other crimes. Based on the many modus operandi of a crime, sometimes the perpetrator himself does not know or even realizes at all that his crime can leave traces of where the crime was committed. In the provisions of Article 14 paragraph (1) letter h of the Law No. 2 Concerning the Police of the Republic of Indonesia, that one of the duties of the Police is to carry out Police identification, Police Medicine, Police forensic and psychological laboratories for the purposes of Police duties. The implementation of Police identification is intended for the purpose of investigating criminal acts and providing non-criminal identification services for the public and other agencies in the context of carrying out Police functions.

In the investigation process there is a special unit that is the police to collect evidence to assist the process of investigating a case, this special unit is called INAFIS (Indonesia Automatic Fingerprint System). This unit is a technical implementing element at the Criminal Investigation Unit, which is under the auspices of the Directorate of Investigation and Crime, the identification unit is tasked with fostering and carrying out identification functions including criminal dactyloscopic activities, general dactyloscopying, and police photography. This unit is led by a section head/sie ident who is responsible to the Directorate of Criminal Investigation and the implementation of daily tasks under the Deputy Directorate of Criminal Investigation. (Jogja POLRI, 2022)

To get good results through fingerprint identification, knowledge is needed to know, understand and understand fingerprint clarification as well as expertise and experience that can distinguish and determine whether fingerprints are identical or not from the same fingerprint. Fingerprints are one of the physical evidences that can be considered as proof of identification of people, so that they can know and determine the identification of the perpetrators of crimes. Sufficient initial evidence in processing the investigation that can be used as a tool. One of the physical evidence that is generally found at crime scenes is fingerprints, namely traces of fingerprints, palms, soles of feet left on the surface of objects at the crime scene, after the object was touched or stepped on. Finding fingerprints on objects at the crime scene will further assist Polri investigators in conducting investigations of these crimes because in this case the characteristics of the perpetrators of crimes will be easier to identify. (Anny Yuserlina, 2017)

Searching for the truth about all events caused by human actions is difficult and not easy because in an event there is often a shortage, and incomplete evidence or witnesses, so that investigators must work harder in collecting valid evidence for investigations. obtain the complete truth in investigating or investigating an actual crime. In Article 1 point 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code, the investigative process is a series of investigative actions in matters and according to the methods stipulated in the law to seek and collect evidence with which evidence makes it clear about the crime that occurred and to find the suspect. In proving a criminal procedure, there must be at least two valid pieces of evidence as the basis for imposing a sentence on the defendant (Article 183 of the Criminal Procedure Code). According to Article 184 of the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP), it is stated that valid evidence is: Witness statements, expert statements, letters, instructions, statements of the accused

Crimes that require dactyloscopy as a means of proof, for example the crime of intentional or premeditated murder and other crimes. Based on the many modus operandi of a crime, sometimes the perpetrator himself does not know or even does not realize at all that his crime can leave traces of where the crime was committed. Traces that will be left at the crime scene are known as latent fingerprints. Latent fingerprints will be very important for an investigator to uncover a case and at the same time determine who the real perpetrators are. (M. Karjadi, 1971)

An investigator taking fingerprints from someone should be careful, thorough and not just obey the will of the person whose fingerprints are to be taken. If this happens, of course it will be very detrimental to the investigators themselves, because it will result in a lack of clarity on the papillary lines. The more fingerprints taken, the more complete the fingerprint archive will be

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owned by the police, because if one day there is a crime case where fingerprints are used as proof, it will be very helpful in the criminal investigation and justice process.

Based on Article 183 of Law Number 8 of 1981 concerning the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP), it can be concluded that before a judge imposes a sentence on the defendant, the judge needs 2 pieces of evidence. This evidence serves to strengthen the judge's conviction of the crime committed by the defendant. As one of the big cities in Central Java, Semarang is a metropolitan city, opportunities for criminal acts to occur are very open, and one of them is the crime committed by teenagers who occurred Semarang City, Crimes in the City of Semarang during 2021 decreased by 24 cases compared to the previous year. Even so, the number of murder cases is still high. Most cases of murder by 25 percent (independence vote)

Based on the description on the background above, the writing of this article is entitled: The Role of Inafis Dactyloscopy in the Murder Investigation Process (Case Study at the Central Java Regional Police)

1. Formulation of the problem

This research wants to find answers to the following research questions:

1. How Role Investigative Dactyloscopy To Determine The Murderer
2. inhibiting factors Dactyloscopy inaphy Investigation to determine the perpetrators of the murder

B. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses an empirical juridical method which according to Fred N Kerlner the empirical juridical itself: as questions that are tried to find answers. It can be concluded that the author wants to approach the role of fingerprints in the investigation process both from a juridical aspect (laws and regulations) as well as from an implementation aspect in society (police) (Khuzafah Dimiyati and Kelk Wardiono, 2008).

To support this research, primary data is needed, namely data sourced from field research by conducting an interview process, and accompanied by secondary data, namely laws and regulations, literature books, magazines, articles, papers, and dictionaries.

The type of data used in this study is qualitative data, namely data that is not in the form of numbers and is obtained from observations, recordings, interviews or written materials (laws, documents, books, etc.) in the form of verbal expressions.

C. DISCUSSION

1. The Role of Inafist Dactyloscopy in the Investigative Process to Determine the Murderer

In the provisions of Article 14 paragraph (1) letter (h) of Law No. 2 Concerning the Police of the Republic of Indonesia, that one of the duties of the Police is to carry out Police identification, Police Medicine, Police forensic and psychological laboratories for the purposes of Police duties. Normatively, the role of the identification unit in assisting the process of investigating a criminal act of murder is found in Article 14 Paragraph (1) letter h of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police which states that one of the duties of the police is "organizing police identification, police medicine, police forensic and psychology laboratories for the benefit of police duties. Regarding the role of fingerprints as evidence in seeking the truth in a crime, it has a legal basis which is the basis for the police in carrying out prosecution of a crime by using evidence in the form of fingerprints in this case that the concrete form of information on a fingerprint in a case The crime can be in the form of a statement made by an expert (Article 187 letter c of the Criminal Procedure Code) which can be qualified as documentary evidence. In addition, if necessary, both during the investigation process at the police and the process of examining a case in court, a Dactyloscopic expert can be summoned to hear his statement to explain the link between the existence of a person's fingerprints in a criminal incident (Marisa Dewi Astuti, 2009)

The crime of murder is a crime committed in the form of attacking the lives of other people. The crime of murder committed intentionally in the Criminal Code is regulated in Book Two Chapter XIX Article 338 to Article 350 concerning Crimes Against Life (Besse Muqita Rijal Mentari, 2019)

Every criminal act of murder is usually based on a variety of motives, such as politics, jealousy, revenge, and so on. Murder can be committed in various ways, the most common of which is by using a gun or knife. In an examination of a criminal act of murder, just like an examination in general, in a criminal case more emphasis is placed on the process of proving. Evidence plays an important role in the process of examining court proceedings, and is the central point of examining cases in court proceedings. Through proof the fate of the accused is determined, because with this proof it can be known whether the defendant really committed the criminal act he was charged with or not. With the existence of evidence, it can be determined the punishment that will be imposed on the defendant who has been proven guilty. The investigative steps carried out by the investigator start from visiting the crime scene, checking what the criminal has done, taking pictures and making sketches, searching for evidence left behind, especially physical tools such as fingerprints that are possible on tools. said, examination of witnesses or victims if alive and people who are considered capable of providing information, searching and processing as well as arrests

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According to police officials at the Semarang City Polrestabes Identification Unit, in this case the Head of Identification Affairs said that, There are several aspects that need to be considered in The pattern of handling carried out by the police, which in this case is the role of the identification unit in uncovering a crime, is: Fingerprints as Evidence, in an era that is as sophisticated and modern as today, POLRI is required to develop following technological advances and developments. From the understanding of Article 183 of the Criminal Procedure Code, Judges in making decisions must consider at least 2 pieces of evidence that can increase confidence The judge in court, in Article 184 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Procedure Code, valid evidence is: witness statement; expert testimony; letter; instruction; and the testimony of the accused.

Article 186 of the Criminal Procedure Code states that " an expert's statement is what an expert states in the field of court " . Police Rights in Overriding Criminal Acts . As law enforcers, the police are included in the ranks of the criminal justice system, as one of the subsystems. The other subsystems are the Prosecutor's Office, Judiciary and Corrections. In the criminal justice system, the police are the gateway for whether or not someone can enter criminal justice. This is where everything starts.

The police's duties as investigators in the criminal justice system place them at the forefront, so that the police are required to be able to select or sort out which cases are appropriate to be brought to court or not based on statutory regulations. Without selection by the Police at the time of investigation there will be a buildup of cases which will be inefficient for all parties

Based on the above data, in handling homicide cases handled by the identification unit, in handling crime scenes to find suspects, the Identification Unit has a very dominant role in gathering evidence for further investigations saying that: in the handling process, there are several stages carried out in dealing with the murder case, which include: Securing victims and evidence , Securing the scene of the incident. Security for the parties involved. Taking samples suspected of having the perpetrator's fingerprints. Looking for items that are suspected of being used by the perpetrator. Pick up the fingerprint and then pour it on the AK23 for fingerprint comparison . Seizure of evidence. Image capture . Crime scene sketch. Make an official report on the results of the comparison of fingerprints and the management of the crime scene obtained (evidence), then submit it to the authorized investigator. After the fingerprints are found, the officer must ensure the location of the latent fingerprints on the surface to be developed and lifted or transferred to the lifter in the following way: Using a flashlight from a certain angle the latent fingerprints are on a clear object surface ; By bringing the officer's head closer to the surface of the object and looking at it from various angles; Blowing off the surface of the object provides moisture that allows latent fingerprints to be seen .

A security guard at the Focus Nusantara Camera Shop who was in the former Jonas Photo building, Jalan Diponegoro No. 45, Lempongsari Village, Gajahmungkur District, Semarang City allegedly killed by being stabbed with a sharp weapon. There was an alleged criminal act of robbery in the case of the death of a security guard named Supriono who guarded the Focus Nusantara Camera shop, in the ex Jonas Photo building, Jalan Diponegoro No.45 ,Lempongsari Village, Gajahmungkur District, Semarang City. The suspicion was strengthened after there was supporting evidence at the scene.

The Central Java Regional Police, based on the evidence at the TKP, then developed an investigation and succeeded in arresting the suspect in Kebumen. It is strongly suspected that the perpetrator immediately fled to his place of origin after carrying out the action," Kombespol Djuhandani Rahardjo Puro (Dirreskrimum Polda Central Java)

interim examination, his party found indications of attempted robbery carried out by an unknown person before the victim was found lifeless in front of Kita Steak which is not far from the location where the victim works . We get this information after the Inafis Team The Central Java Police found several robbery tools such as a welding machine and other suspects' belongings, namely a backpack containing other equipment. Our suspicion is that there was an attempt to commit a robbery or 365 (Article Concerning Theft with Violence) (power of kata.com)

Kombespol Djuhandani Rahardjo Puro " that after visiting the crime scene, a crime scene (TKP) was held, namely checking the way the perpetrator entered and left the crime scene and examined what the perpetrator had done. In carrying out processing of the crime scene, the identification unit team coordinates with investigators in conducting processing of the crime scene. as a whole, namely by taking pictures of the crime scene in general, searching for evidence that was left behind, especially physical tools such as fingerprints that are possible on these tools, taking detailed pictures of evidence, and conducting a search for perpetrators or suspects by asking for information from eyewitnesses in the scene of the incident by recording as necessary (identity) what he saw and heard himself. (Dirreskrimum Polda Central Java)

Kombespol Djuhandani Rahardjo Puro explained that after removing the latent fingerprints , the officer would carry out an examination and comparison of fingerprints by matching the latent fingerprints found at the crime scene with the fingerprints of the suspected person. Before the latent fingerprints found at the crime scene are compared with the fingerprints stored in files stored in the police database on behalf of a particular person, the latent fingerprints are first compared with the fingerprints of people who have legally held the crime scene and also those who suspected. The aim is to narrow the search for suspects (Diresskrimum Polda Central Java)

Kombespol Djuhandani Rahardjo Puro states that the role of the identification unit in assisting the process of investigating a crime of murder is to support efforts to search for and collect evidence at the TKP. (Dirreskrimum Polda Central Java). After the evidence has been collected, the next process is scientifically examined so that the evidence can be set forth in the form of an examination report. The results of the examination can be used as evidence, namely letters or expert statements in evidence as stipulated in Article 183 and Article 184 of the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP).

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Based on the descriptions with the informants, the authors analyze that the role of the identification unit in the process of investigating the criminal act of murder is in accordance with the normative role and the factual role. The normative role is carried out based on statutory regulations, especially Law no. 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police. Whereas the factual role is carried out based on concrete reality in the field or social life that occurs in real terms, which is carried out with steps starting with receiving a report from the field investigation team of a criminal act, then visiting the scene of the case, conducting TKP processing, developing and removal of latent fingerprints and then comparing the fingerprints found at the crime scene with the fingerprints of suspected persons and/or data held by the police database and then processing them at the general crime laboratory in the identification section to carry out fingerprint examination and comparison. After that, the results of the comparative examination are made in the form of an official report to be submitted to the authorized investigator as a statement stating that the perpetrator's fingerprints are identical or not identical to the comparison fingerprints used.

2. Factors that hinder Inafist Dactyloscopy Investigation Process to Determine the Murderer

Investigators in finding fingerprint evidence in investigations often encounter obstacles or even fail to collect evidence from the crime scene (TKP). The obstacles that investigators will encounter in the activities carried out by the identification unit (Inafis) to assist the investigation are divided into several factors, including:

1. Law Enforcement Factors

The law enforcement factor that hinders the identification unit in assisting the process of investigating the crime of murder from a law enforcement perspective is the lack of capability of the identification officer's Human Resources (HR). Officer factors have a very dominant role in processing crime scenes in order to collect evidence for further investigations. The ability of officers to identify is an important element in finding evidence, the ability of officers who lack knowledge about identification will find it difficult to find evidence or even damage the traces of the perpetrators who should be used as evidence

Identification units also play a role in terms of public services to the community. So that the officers will be divided in carrying out their duties. For this reason, the limited number of identification unit personnel at the Central Java Regional Police has also become an obstacle in assisting the process of investigating a crime of murder

2. Facility Factors and Facilities

Factors and facilities that hinder the identification unit in assisting the process of investigating a crime of murder is the lack of equipment to support identification so that the implementation of identification is not optimal, for example the lack of supporting equipment for identification such as the absence of digital tools to sketch facial expressions. by the identification unit at the central level, namely Mabes Polri (Headquarters of the Indonesian National Police).

The most dominant factor hindering the role of the identification unit in assisting the process of investigating a crime of murder is the facility factor.

3. Community Factor

is the factor that most often becomes an obstacle or obstacle to the identification unit in assisting the murder investigation process. This is due to the lack of public knowledge about the processing of the crime scene (TKP).

In general, if a crime occurs and is known by the public, then the people around the TKP with a great sense of curiosity about the incident, will spontaneously go straight to the scene of the case to see firsthand the incident and accidentally the community has destroying the crime scene evidence as well as in assessing or analyzing the events that occurred. When the crime scene is damaged or disturbed, such as changing the position of evidence or the loss of evidence from the crime scene and increasing fingerprints, it certainly creates obstacles in carrying out an investigation. This will be difficult for officers.

D. CONCLUSION

From the discussion that has been described above, we can conclude the following:

The basis for the ema plestabas police in carrying out prosecution of a crime is by using evidence in the form of fingerprints in this case that the concrete form of a statement on a fingerprint in a criminal case can be in the form of a statement made by an expert (Article 187 letter c of the Criminal Procedure Code) which can be qualified as documentary evidence. The function of fingerprint identification as the main means of evidence in the crime of premeditated murder which is included in the investigation process is to assist the police in identifying matching identities suspected as perpetrators which provide accurate evidence in the investigative process to determine suspects in the crime of murder. Obstacle factors encountered by investigators in activities carried out by the identification unit to assist investigations are divided into 2 factors, namely external factors and internal factors including: Law Enforcement Factors, Facilities and Facilities Factors, Community Factors

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